

The Development Strategy of Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region in Palopo City

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Abstract:- The unoptimal development of Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region in Palopo City has resulted in decreased tourist visits number. This study aims to identify and analyze the supporting factors and inhibiting factors and to formulate a development strategy for Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region in Palopo City. This study is a descriptive study with mixed methods approach between quantitative and qualitative analysis. SWOT analysis is used to analyze the existing factors of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats and formulate the right development strategy. The findings indicate that the biggest strength and weakness are the good accessibility and the absence of development Master Plan. While the biggest opportunity and threat are the existence of large vacant land and the river condition with floods, overflows and landslides threat. The strategy position is in Quadrant I, namely Aggressive Strategy (S-O) with strategy alternatives: improvement of tourism promotion, formulation of a sustainable development Master Plan, establishing a one-stop payment system, developing creative economy, and improving security.

Keywords:- Development Strategy, Natural Bath Tourism, SWOT Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism serves as a driving factor or source of energy for sustainable development for an area that develops it [1]. The development of tourism areas in South Sulawesi, especially in Palopo City, which includes the development of natural tourism regions by relying on natural potential and wealth along with improvement of the quality of the environment is directed at Natural Tourism Parks (TWA) such as natural bath tourism or rafting [2,3,4,5].

One of the natural tourism park-based tourist destinations in the city of Palopo is Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region, which has currently not been optimally developed. The problem faced is that there is a lack of tourism promotion and the utilization of tourism potential has not been optimized in order to increase tourist visits [6].

According to data on tourist visits to Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region, from 2019 to 2021 the number of tourists has decreased drastically, namely $\pm 2,000$ tourists per year. This decrease reached around 27% in 2020 and 43% in

2021. The decrease in the number of tourists will greatly affect the amount of the retribution generated [7].

A. Problem Statement

Based on the background stated in the previous section, the problem statement in this study is: What are the factors that support and inhibit the development of the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City?; What is the development strategy for the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City?

B. Study Objectives

According to the background and problem statement that has been described previously, the objectives of this study are: to identify and analyze the supporting factors and inhibiting factors in the development of Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City; to formulate a development strategy for the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City.

II. METHODS

A. Type of Study

This study is a descriptive study with mixed method approach between quantitative and qualitative analysis [8].

B. Time and Location of Study

This study was conducted in December 2022 at Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region, a tourism object located in Padang Lambe Village, Wara Barat District, Palopo City. Geographically this area is located at coordinates of $2^{\circ}55'52.5''$ South Latitude and $120^{\circ}08'30.1''$ East Longitude and is at an altitude of ± 120 meters above sea level (masl). Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region has a distance of ± 15 Km or about 30 minutes from the center of Palopo City.

C. Population and Sample

➤ Population

The population of this study is the average number of tourists visiting from 2019 to 2022, namely 5,354 people and the person in charge or manager of the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City.

➤ Sample

Based on the results of calculations using Slovin Formula, the number of tourist samples is 98 people, using simple random sampling technique. As for the sources for this

study, they are employees of the Office of Tourism and Creative Economy of the City of Palopo along with self-help groups who are responsible for and carry out management and supervision of the tourism region [9].

D. Data Collection and Analysis

➤ Data Collection

The data required in this study are primary data in the form of survey results and interviews with respondents and informants; and secondary data in the form of documents originating from related institutions and study results. [10]

➤ Data Analysis

The discussion in this study uses descriptive analysis and SWOT analysis. Descriptive analysis to describe the phenomenon and actual conditions that occur in the field and summarize the findings of internal and external factors that support and inhibit the process of developing the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City [11].

SWOT analysis is used to design a development strategy for the Batu Papan Nature Tourism Region in Palopo City. The steps in the SWOT analysis include: Analysis of internal factors and external factors; Determination of the variable weights of internal factors and external factors; Rating Determination; Compilation of Alternative Strategies; and Making a matrix of alternative SWOT analysis strategies [12].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Tourists Characteristics

Based on the results of a survey conducted on 104 respondents, it is observed that the majority of tourists come from South Sulawesi Province as much as 97%. The age group of 31-40 years is the age group with the largest number (56%). Male tourists represent 51% and female tourists represent 49%. The State Civil Apparatus is the tourist which has the largest number (41%). The most education level of the tourists is tertiary education (84.6%). Tourists with an income of 2-5 million rupiahs per month represents the largest number of them (50%). The average number of tourist visits is around 25% who visit 1 (one) time, 2 (two) times, 3 (three) to more than 5 (five) times.

B. Tourist Responses

Overall, tourists responses to tourism components [13,14] are grouped into several sections, including:

- For accessibility such as travel time, road conditions, and signpost, according to tourists it can be categorized as good. Meanwhile, the availability of public transportation is still inadequate
- According to tourists, the existing attractions already have good appeal, as well as several attractions that can be developed in the future to add to their attractiveness, which also received a very good response.
- Several facilities, means and infrastructure in Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City can be

categorized to be adequate such as parking lots, roads within the area, toilets and clean water. However, there are still many vital facilities that need to be added, improved and rejuvenated to support tourism activities in it. These facilities, means and infrastructure include accommodation such as home stays that are currently not available; restaurant-class cook shop that do currently not exist, there are only street stalls; an abandoned information center and souvenir sales building; inadequate security, protection and safety facilities; as well as telecommunication and internet networks which are very difficult to access in tourism location.

- In terms of institutions and human resources, the response from tourists is low. Officers in tourist areas are not sufficient and adequate, whether those who are in charge of maintaining security, safety, or other officers whose main tasks and functions are demanded in the development of the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City.
- Conditions within and around the tourism location are still relatively safe. Most tourists respond disagree to unfavorable issues and conflicts that can interfere with comfort and safety. However, there is a need for an alert of the threat of flooding and landslides around the river, particularly in extreme weather conditions.
- Tourism promotion needs to be improved, both offline (billboards, posters or pamphlets) and online (such as social media), which of course should be accompanied by the development of all aspects that increase tourist attraction. The existence of other tourist objects around may be a threat, but overall tourists consider that a visit to Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City is a good choice of visit, worth revisiting, worth recommending to others, and has more benefits than other tourist destinations.

C. Identification and Analysis of Internal and External Factors

To identify what factors influence the development of the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City, interviews were conducted with 5 (five) informants. The results of the interviews were then analyzed and combined with the results of the tourist questionnaire recapitulation to obtain internal factors (strengths and weaknesses) and external factors (opportunities and threats).

The next step is to formulate a questionnaire to determine the weight and rating of each of these factors. Respondents in this questionnaire are informants who have been interviewed before in identifying these factors. The reason is that the information obtained is more accurate and complementary to one another. The results of the recapitulation of the weight and rating questionnaires are compiled into the IFAS (Internal Strategic Factor Analysis Summary) Matrix Table and the EFAS (External Strategic Factor Analysis Summary) Matrix Table which can be seen in tables 1 and 2.

Table 1 IFAS Matrix of Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region

No.	Internal Factors	Weight	Rating	Score	Rank
Strengths					
1.	Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City has excellence attractiveness	0.059	4.25	0.252	S3
2.	Has more than one type of tourist attraction	0.056	3.75	0.210	S7
3.	Good accessibility and road conditions	0.063	4.75	0.297	S1
4.	Close distance from neighboring districts	0.056	4.5	0.252	S4
5.	Relatively cheap retribution rates and gazebo rental fees	0.059	4.5	0.266	S2
6.	Electricity and clean water are available	0.053	4	0.211	S6
7.	Security within and around the tourist area is conducive	0.043	4.25	0.182	S8
8.	Adequate physical facilities	0.039	3	0.118	S9
9.	Already good tourism promotion	0.033	2.75	0.090	S10
10.	The existence of Tourism-Aware Group that provide assistance in the tourism region management	0.059	4.25	0.252	S5
Strengths Total Score				2.129	
Weaknesses					
1.	Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City does not currently have a development Master Plan	0.056	1	0.056	W1
2.	The distance from the center of Palopo City is relatively distant.	0.046	2.75	0.127	W9
3.	Public transportation and tourism services are inadequate	0.049	2.25	0.111	W8
4.	Limited budget for the construction and maintenance of facilities and infrastructure	0.059	1.25	0.074	W2
5.	Lack of quantity and quality of managing human resources	0.046	2.25	0.104	W6
6.	Telecommunication/internet infrastructure and networks are very limited	0.066	1.5	0.099	W5
7.	The availability of restaurants and cook shop is currently inadequate.	0.059	1.25	0.074	W3
8.	There is currently no accommodation and lodging	0.059	1.25	0.074	W4
9.	Cleanliness in the tourism region has not been maintained	0.039	2.75	0.109	W7
Weaknesses Total Score				0.826	
The difference between Strengths and Weaknesses is (S – W) = 2.129 – 0.826 = 1.303					

Table 2 EFAS Matrix of Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region

No.	External Factors	Weight	Rating	Score	Rank
Opportunities					
1.	The availability of large vacant land that can be utilized	0.084	5	0.418	O1
2.	Development of the community's creative economy in terms of making and selling souvenirs or local products	0.071	4.5	0.320	O5
3.	The large number of tourists who want to visit	0.054	3.5	0.190	O8
4.	Development toward Agrotourism and Edutourism	0.075	4.5	0.339	O3
5.	Collaboration with third parties in terms of preparing the Master Plan, construction and development of facilities and tourist attractions	0.075	4.25	0.320	O6
6.	Collaboration with related agencies to increase HR and management capabilities	0.075	4.5	0.339	O4
7.	Development of other infrastructure that supports the development of tourism region	0.071	4.5	0.320	O7
8.	Tourism-aware group and the surrounding community work together in developing tourism region	0.079	4.5	0.358	O2
Opportunities Total Score				2.605	
Threats					
1.	The condition of the river which often floods and overflows as well as the threat of landslides	0.079	1.25	0.099	T1
2.	Tourism region do not have protective fences from livestock and wild animals	0.084	1.25	0.105	T2
3.	Communities residing arounded the tourism region have not fully supported development	0.059	2.75	0.161	T6
4.	Poor awareness of the public and tourists in maintaining cleanliness	0.063	2.5	0.157	T5
5.	There is illegal racing activity in tourism region	0.071	1.75	0.124	T3
6.	The existence of similar/non-similar tourist attractions that are more interesting	0.059	2.25	0.132	T4
Threats Total Score				0.778	
The difference between Opportunities and Threats is (O – T) = 2.605 – 0.778 = 1.826					

Based on the results of weights and ratings calculation on the IFAS Matrix, it can be observed that accessibility and good road conditions are the Strength Factors which have the highest rating of 4.75 with a score of 0.297. Then followed by retribution rates and gazebo rental fees which are relatively cheap with a rating of 4.5 and with a score of 0.266. As for the Weaknesses, the lower the rating and score, the greater the weakness. In the IFAS Matrix, it can be observed that Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City does not yet have a Development Master Plan, which is the biggest weakness with a rating of 1 and a score of 0.056, followed by limited budget for the construction and maintenance of facilities and infrastructure with a rating of 1.25 and a score of 0.074.

Based on the results of weights and ratings calculation on the EFAS Matrix, it can be observed that there is still a lot of vacant land that can be utilized. The Opportunities Factor has the highest rating, namely 5 with a score of 0.418. Then followed by tourism-aware group and the surrounding community working together in building a tourist area which has a rating of 4.5 with a score of 0.358. Meanwhile, for Threats, the lower the rating and score, the greater the threat. In the EFAS Matrix, it can be observed that the condition of

the river which often floods and overflows as well as the threat of landslides is the biggest weakness factor with a rating of 1.25 and a score of 0.099, followed by tourist areas that do not have protective fences from livestock and wild animals with a rating of 1.25 and a score of 0.105.

D. Identification of Strategy Position

In the IFAS Matrix, it can be observed that the total score for the Strengths Factor is 2,129 and the total score for Weaknesses is 0.826. The difference in the total score of strengths and weaknesses is $2.129 - 0.826 = 1.303$ which means that the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region in Palopo City has advantages in terms of strengths to build and formulate development strategies. Then the total score is converted into the value of the SWOT Grand Matrix Strategy diagram on the X axis.

In the EFAS Matrix, the total score for the Opportunities Factor is 2.605 and the total score for the Threats is 0.778. The difference between the total Opportunity and Threat scores is $2.605 - 0.778 = 1.826$. The total score is then converted into the value of the Grand Matrix Strategy SWOT diagram on the Y axis. For more details, the Grand Matrix Strategy SWOT diagram can be seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Grand Matrix Strategy SWOT Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City

The diagram shows that the identification of strategy position point is in Quadrant I, namely Aggressive Strategy (S – O). This strategy is developed by utilizing all strengths to seize and take advantage of as many opportunities as possible. In other words, the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City needs to maximize all of its Strengths to seize the Opportunities that have been available so far, namely by utilizing the existing potential that can support the development of tourist areas in a better direction.

E. Strategy Formulation

The strategy used in the development of Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region in Palopo City is more focused on the S – O strategy. The strategy that needs be applied in this condition is a strategy that supports aggressive growth policies (growth oriented strategy). For more details, several alternative development strategies that have been prepared based on the results of the analysis can be seen in table 3.

Table 3 Strategy Matrix S – O for The Development of Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region in Palopo City

<p>S – O Strategy</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Strengths</u></p> <p>S1 Good accessibility and road conditions S2 Relatively cheap retribution rates and gazebo rental fees S3 Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region of Palopo City has excellence attractiveness S4 Close distance from neighboring districts S5 The existence of Tourism-Aware Group that provide assistance in the tourism region management S6 Electricity and clean water are available S7 Has more than one type of tourist attractions S8 Security within and around the tourist area is conducive S9 Adequate physical facilities S10 Already good tourism promotion</p>
<p style="text-align: center;"><u>Opportunities</u></p> <p>O1 The availability of large vacant land that can be utilized O2 Tourism-aware group and the surrounding community work together in developing tourism region O3 Development toward Agrotourism and Edutourism O4 Collaboration with related agencies to increase HR and management capabilities O5 Development of the community's creative economy in terms of making and selling souvenirs or local products O6 Collaboration with third parties in terms of preparing the Master Plan, construction and development of facilities and tourist attractions O7 Development of other infrastructure that supports the development of tourism region O8 The large number of tourists who want to visit</p>	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>S1 S2 S4 S6 S7 S9 S10 – O3 O5 O7 O8</u></p> <p>Promotion of tourism to other districts needs improvement to invite more tourists from outside the town. This is supported by good accessibility and road conditions, relatively cheap retribution rates, adequate facilities and infrastructure, and infrastructure development which in the future can add to tourist attractiveness.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>S3 S5 S7 S9 – O1 O2 O3 O6 O7</u></p> <p>The large amount of unused vacant land is a huge opportunity for the manager to work with third parties to prepare a Master Plan for the development and development of facilities and infrastructure as well as tourist attractions that lead to the development of sustainable agrotourism and edutourism</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>S2 S3 S7 S9 – O3 O4 O5 O6</u></p> <p>Establishing a one-stop payment system consisting of retribution fees, attractions, product purchases, and rental (facilities, goods and services) available in the tourism region</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>S3 S5 S7 – O2 O4 O5</u></p> <p>Tourism-aware group collaborate with relevant agencies in developing the creative economy by conducting counseling and training to communities around tourism region for the manufacture and sale of souvenirs and local products</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>S5 S8 – O2 O4</u></p> <p>Tourism-aware groups and the community work together with relevant agencies to improve security both inside and around the tourism region which is supported by training and human resource development</p>

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The supporting and inhibiting factors in the development of the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region in Palopo city include: the biggest strength is accessibility and good road conditions with a rating of 4.75 and a score of 0.297; the biggest weakness is that the Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region in Palopo City does not yet have a Development Master Plan with a rating of 1 and a score of 0.056; the biggest opportunity is the availability of vacant land that can be utilized with a rating of 5 and a score of 0.418; the biggest threat (treath) is the condition of the river which often floods and overflows and the threat of landslides with a rating of 1.25 and a score of 0.099.

The strategy position point for Batu Papan Natural Bath Tourism Region development is identified in Quadrant I, namely Aggressive Strategy (S-O). This strategy utilizes all

strengths to seize and take advantage of as many opportunities as possible. The alternatives to the S–O strategy include:

- Promotion of tourism to other districts needs improvement to invite more tourists from outside the town. This is supported by good accessibility and road conditions, relatively cheap retribution rates, adequate facilities and infrastructure, and infrastructure development which in the future can add to tourist attractiveness.
- The large amount of unused vacant land is a huge opportunity for the manager to work with third parties to prepare a Master Plan for the development and development of facilities and infrastructure as well as tourist attractions that lead to the development of sustainable agrotourism and edutourism
- Establishing a one-stop payment system consisting of retribution fees, attractions, product purchases, and rental (facilities, goods and services) available in the tourism region

- Tourism-aware group collaborate with relevant agencies in developing the creative economy by conducting counseling and training to communities around tourism region for the manufacture and sale of souvenirs and local products
- Tourism-aware group and the community work together with relevant agencies to improve security both inside and around the tourism region which is supported by training and human resource development.

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